

**COMPARATIVE STUDY OF LEXICAL AND GRAMMATICAL
PECULIARITIES OF STATIVE VERBS IN THE ENGLISH AND UZBEK
LANGUAGES**

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ABSTRACT: In this article important features of verbs in English and Uzbek languages were discussed. Through this article peculiarities of state verbs, their function and ways of usage in both languages were noted.

KEY WORDS: *dynamic, stative, integral seme, duration, result of ovement, execution, movement, skill, imagery, biological, confidently.*

Every English sentence must have a verb. The verb could be classified as dynamic, stative, or both. A dynamic verb describes an action; a stative verb describes a condition. This classification is important because it determines how the verb can and cannot be used. Knowing the difference between stative and dynamic verbs will help you speak and write correctly and avoid basic errors in exams or emails, as well as in many social, academic, and business situations. Dynamic verbs describe action. Examples are run, jump, work, play, eat, or drink. They are the most common type of verb and can be used correctly in all verb tenses and aspects. They are usually the easiest to learn. Stative verbs describe states or conditions. They can be used in simple and perfect tenses and aspects. However, they cannot be used in the continuous or progressive forms. This limitation makes stative verbs a little more difficult to master, which means practice is necessary. Dynamic/Stative verbs can be used in either way, depending on the context or

meaning. Examples are have, think, and feel. These verbs are usually the most challenging because there’s no one rule; you have to think about each situation separately. Practice is essential. However, by paying careful attention, you can learn to use these unusual verbs correctly and confidently.

State verbs in the sentences are realized in the active, reflexive, compulsive, passive and mutual voices. State verbs with integral seme «duration», «result of movement», «execution», «movement», «skill», «imagery», «biological», «physiological» and «psychic» – are realized in speech mostly in the active voice. The agent of this verbs finds expression in the character of the object. The agent of some state verbs with the integral seme «result of movement», «execution», «imagery», «physiological» and «psychic» do not appear as functions of the object in sentence. Agent's non-objectivity, but only its subjectivity, follows from the transitivity of certain state verbs. The agent of some transitive state verbs with the integral seme «execution» and «psychic», even though they have own object, they are not only the producer (source) of the state, but also the object of the produced state. The possibility of combining state verbs with a direct object, that means, their transitivity deserves special attention. State verbs with the integral seme «execution», «physiological» and «psychic» are realized in the sentence in a reflexive voice. Agent is an object in all cases. Verbs with the integral seme «duration», «result of movement», «movement», «biological», «physiological» and «psychic» are realized in speech in a compulsory voice. Stative verbs (or state verbs) have the following characteristics:

- ✓ They express a state rather than an action;
- ✓ They refer to thoughts, senses, emotions, feelings, and possessions;
- ✓ They are not usually used in the continuous (progressive) tenses (i.e. with -ing);
- ✓ Some verbs can be used as both state verbs and action verbs;

So as opposed to action verbs, they reflect a mental process rather than a dynamic activity. For example:

•I am playing football tomorrow (= action)

I went to town yesterday (= action)

•I think I will go to town (= a thought)

I hate spicy food (= an emotion)

There is not one way to classify them and words could fit in various categories, but here are some common examples of stative verbs placed into four common categories. Here are some stative verb sentences using these verbs. Remember these state verbs cannot be used in the continuous tenses.

➤ Thoughts - I doubt she will go tonight;

➤ Emotions - She adores her children;

➤ Senses - He smells very bad;

➤ Possession- That bag belongs to me;

We also use stative verbs for measurements, costs, and weights, so again these are not used in the continuous tenses: He weighs 190 kilograms;

Some verbs can express both an action and a state. However, they are usually being used to convey a different type of meaning in each case. Action verbs refer to something dynamic, such as some kind of activity, rather than stative verbs, which reflect a state of mind or a mental process. Here are some examples. As you can see, the action verbs can be in the continuous tense.

State: I have a car (= possession/ownership)

Action: I'm having a good time (= the action of enjoying oneself)

State: I see you have a new coat (= sense/perception)

Action: I'm seeing John now (= the action of having a relationship)

The verbs of state in the Uzbek language according to the extra-linguistic substrate express a huge number of processes associated with natural phenomena, the formation of thinking and human behavior, etc. In the process of analyzing state verbs in the Uzbek language by their semantic components, the following lexical-semantic groups of this semantic field were identified:

- 1) verbs of a continuous state,
- 2) verbs of a state that is the result of movement,
- 3) verbs of a performance state,
- 4) the verbs of the state of motion,
- 5) the verbs of the state of skill,
- 6) the verbs of the figurative state,
- 7) the verbs of the biological state,
- 8) the verbs of the physiological state,

9) the verbs of the psychic state. In these lexical-semantic groups, «state» is an archisema, and «duration», «result of movement», «execution», «movement», «skill», «imagery», «biological», «physiological» and «psychic» - an integral seme within its lexicalesemantic group.

The agent actant of state verbs in the active voice with the integral seme «duration» (turmoq 'to stand', o'tirmoq 'to sit', yotmoq 'to lie'), «result of movement» (to'xtamoq 'to stop', tinmoq 'to rest', zanglamoq 'to rust'), «execution» (salqinlamoq 'to relax in a cool place'), «movement» (kuchaymoq 'strengthen', og'irlashmoq 'get heavy', tezlashmoq 'accelerate'), «skill» (ko'nikmoq, odatlanmoq 'to get used to'), «imagery» (alangalanmoq 'to ignition', mixlanmoq 'to be nailed', qaqqaymoq 'stick up'), «biological» (qarimoq 'getting old', chanqamoq 'to be thirsty', gullamoq

'blooming'), «physiological» (uxlamoq 'to sleep', ozmoq 'to lose weight', charchamoq 'get tired'), «psychic» (qo'rqmoq 'to afraid', hayajonlanmoq 'exciting', g'azablanmoq 'to get angry') etc. is realized in logical entities of an objective nature.

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